

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	10	B		Min: 63.1001 Max: 63.3083	1180 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 624 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION
Tufo layer below gravel layer (1179) in Room 1

Covered by SU: 1179 Fills SU: Filled by SU:

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? FORMATION PROCESS

Color Composition Compaction Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are

Anthropic	Geological	Organic	SOIL/MATRIX														
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dolia R <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) R <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) orange, f <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones R <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	clay 15% silt 85% sand ___% <input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Compaction</th> <th>Color</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Hard</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Compact</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Friable</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Loose</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Soft</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) orangey</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	<input type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) orangey
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1179	Covers: 1181
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS
Excavated with pick

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: South central
Shape: Irregular patch preserved

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): level

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): Fairly uniform thickness of about 10cm, below gravel layer

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:

Cut edges: rounded straight

Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping

Cut bottom: flat concave irregular

How is cut top edge? sharp rounded

How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded

Observations:

Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):

 = walls

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

Crushed tufo preparation layer for cocciopesto floor surface in Room 1. A second preparation layer of gravel is above tufo layer. Layer is truncated in the rest of the room, along with cocciopesto and gravel layers.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by *S. Roux*

Revised by *CM*

PDFd by *JJM*

Entered by

on *15.07.10*

on *19.07.2010*

on *23.07.2010*

on